

Hans Staden: Warhaftige Historia (1557)

An annotated bibliography on the work, secondary literature and other aspects

By Franz Obermeier and Wolfgang Schiffner

Status: update 2025

Introduction

The memory of Hans Staden in the North Hessian area, from whence he comes, began with the teacher Wilhelm Neuhaus, who gave the lecture "Amerikafahrer Hans Staden from Homberg" at the general meeting of the Knüllgebirgsverein in Homberg on September 20, 1913. (Published in the magazine "Mein Heimatland", third vol., No. 10 and 11, Hoelsche Druckerei in Bad Hersfeld). Further contributions by regional researchers in the following years (see details in Harbsmeier 1997, p.85) showed the growing importance that Hans Staden's work had gained in local research. We only mention Friedrich Sommer and his contribution: Hans Staden von Homberg, der Festungskommandant von Bertioga, in: Heimat-Schollen Nr. 23, 1925, Beilage zum Wolfhager Kreisblatt, 5. Jahrgang, p.178-181 and 186-189.

In 1956 the magazine "Hessische Heimat" published, in volume 6, issue 5, 10 contributions about Staden. Detailed information is provided on many aspects of Staden's life and work. Particularly noteworthy is the contribution of the historian Hilmar Milbradt, who had discovered a letter from Staden to Count Wolrad II. of Waldeck in the State Archives in Marburg. The undated document is an accompanying letter which Staden sent with *his Warhaftige Historia* to the nobleman, signed as "Hanns Staden von Hombergk zu Hessen itzo zum Wolffhagen wonhaftig". Gerhard Menk published this and another letter by Hans Staden in the "Zeitschrift des Vereins für hessische Geschichte und Landeskunde" in 1989, Volume 94, p.63-70. The second letter is another undated accompanying letter which Staden sent with his work to Count Philip of Nassau, the addressee of Johann Dryander's detailed dedication in the *Warhaftige Historia*.

A third document, dated June 4, 1558, can be found in the Hessisches Staatsarchiv Marburg (Best. 157 I, Fragmenta actorum Vol. XXVII, No. 10). It documents that Hans Staden learned to produce saltpeter from a powdermaker in Marburg. He had received 10 thalers and was to deliver the saltpeter he had produced to his master. Since Staden had not fulfilled this former agreement, the licentiate Johannes Keudel sent a letter to a judge in Sachsenberg in the county of Waldeck requesting Staden's payment under threat of arrest. He still assumed that Staden lived in Korbach. These source documents are included with others in the appendix of the digital Staden editions in German, another in Portuguese, both edited by Obermeier 2023 in the original and in respective translation.

Staden in permanent museum exhibitions

In the Heimatmuseum Homberg/Efze, Staden's birthplace, where he was probably born on an unknown date between 1520 and 1530, some copies and translations are exhibited in two showcases added to the collection in the 60s of the 20th century, including a translation into Japanese.

Staden at the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land

Oberlandeskirchenrat Günter E. Th. Bezenberger (1923-1993) had taken a great interest in Staden and his work for many years, in addition to his ecclesiastical tasks. He collected books, woodcuts, copper engravings and many other objects related to the places and areas Staden had visited in Brazil. He was the editor of a facsimile print of the *Warhaftige Historia* in Kassel in 1978. In 1989 he curated an exhibition based on his own collection in the Regional Museum Kaufungen, followed by another in 1990 in the Landeshaus of the Hessian State government in Bonn. Later on, he wanted to ensure that this collection of 102 objects could be permanently displayed. Therefore a foundation was created in Wolfhagen by the city council (Hans Staden-Stiftung). In 1995, a new department with these objects illustrating Staden's travelogue and numerous copies and translations of his work was opened in the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land. This exhibition, which had been conceived and designed by the then incumbent museum director Wolfgang Halfar, can still be seen in the museum with some minor updates. To this day it is the most comprehensive exhibition dedicated to the important German traveller to Brazil in the 16th century. (<http://regionalmuseum-wolfhager-land.de/>).

Future developments at the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land

Thanks to pledged funds from the KulturInvest programme 2024, it will be possible from 2025 on to develop a new concept for the museum's Staden department over several years. In addition to the regional museum at its usual location on Ritterstrasse in Wolfhagen there is to be established another branch with the Staden department in a location at the city centre with a modern multimedia conception. This exhibition shall be accommodated in a historic half-timbered house in Wolfhagen.

This new branch should in addition to the person of Hans Staden also focus on the subject of colonialism and furthermore illuminate and strengthen the cultural relationship between Germany and Brazil.

The Commemoration of Staden's work is present in Wolfhagen and in Homberg. Below are listed the exhibitions and conferences dedicated to Staden in Wolfhagen (and one conference in Homberg). Since 2019 the city of Wolfhagen is entitled to call itself *Hans-Staden-Stadt*. A new Staden monument (see below) has been inaugurated and the so called Staden-Pfad, a path through the city with bronze reliefs inspired by Staden's illustrations, is also finished.

For the Staden-Path see: <https://www.hansstaden.com/>

I. The Work

A. The original edition

Warhaftig^c Historia vnd beschreibung eyner Landt-schafft der Wilden/ Nacketen/ Grimmigen Menschfresser Leuthen/ gelegen in der Newenwelt America/ vor vnd nach Christi geburt im Land zu Hessen vn bekant/ biß vff dise ij. Nechst vergangene jar/ Da sie Hans Staden von Homberg auß Hessen durch sein eygne erfahrung erkant/vnd yetzo durch den truck an tag gibt.

Dedicirt dem Durchleuchtigen Hochgeboꝛnen herꝛn/H. Philipsen Landtgraff zu Hessen/ Graff zu Catzen-elnbogen/ Dietz/ Ziegenhain vnd Nidda/ seinem G. H. [gnädigen Herren]

Mit eyner Vorrede D. Joh. Dryanderi/ genant Eychman/Ordinarij Professoris Medici zu Marburgk.

Inhalt des Büchlins volget nach den Vorreden. Getruckt zu Marburg/ im jar M. D. LVII.

The first edition in Marburg can be dated with the colophon:
 "Zu Marburg im Kleeblatt, bei Andreas Kolben, uff Fasnacht" (Fasnacht is Carnival in German)
 – to the end of February

Size 23 x 17 cm - 178 pages

Dedication to Landgrave Philip of Hesse (3-4), dated 20 June 1556

Preface by Johannes Eichmann, called Dryander (5-14), Professor of anatomy and physician in Marburg (1500-1560) dedicated to Philip III, Count of Nassau and Weilburg, dated on St Thomas' Day 1556 [21 December]

Content (15)

Map (attached), in most original editions bound at the end of the book

Part One: Report on two trips to Brazil (17-124)

Prayer of thanks to God (124-126)

Part Two: On the Customs and Customs of the Tupinambá (127-174), Separate Title Page,

Final speech (175-178)

54 woodcuts (11x11 cm), 1 map, folded.

Print type: Schwabacher. The woodcuts, as a critical remark by Staden in the Errata proves, are based on his preliminary drawings. The artists are not known. The chapter headings could have been added by the printer Andreas Kolbe. Dryander's participation in the book was intensively discussed in the secondary literature, but is probably limited to the preface and a review of the text, to which he was obliged as censor of the university ex officio. Presumably, the division of the work into two "books" with a second ethnographic part in the tradition of cosmography goes back to a proposal by Dryander, who had reedited cosmographies himself.

The immediate success on the book market required another edition in 1557 by Kolbe „Vnd zum andern mal fleissig corrigirt vnd gebessert“ [„and in this second („ander“) edition diligently corrected and improved“] with the colophon "Vff Mariae Geburts tag" (i.e. September 08) to be sold at the Frankfurt autumn Book Fair. The same woodcuts were used. An illustration at the end of the first part showing a religious motto was exchanged with another illustration, just as little related to the text, for details see: Hans Staden, Studienausgabe

German, another ed. in Portuguese, both edited by F. Obermeier 2023). Minor corrections of the errata in the text.

The work was available for sale at the Book Fair in Frankfurt/Main. The success inspired the Frankfurt based printer Weygandt Han to reprint Staden's work this year. The lack of a year on the title page suggested that he was the first printer. Not being in possession of the printing blocks of the original woodcuts, he used 40 woodcuts in the first part which he took from a book he had published earlier. This book was the German translation of a travelogue by the Italian Ludovico de Varthema, who had travelled to Asia from 1501-1507 and had published his book as *Itinerario de Ludouico de Varthema Bolognese*, Rome: Stephano Guillireti de Loreno & maestro Hercule de Nani 1510. These illustrations had been originally made by the artist Jörg Breu der Ältere for a 1515 Varthema edition, *Die ritterlich un lobwirdig Rayss*, published in Augsburg by the printer Miller. Han had published his Varthema edition under the same title in 1556. Thus Staden's travelogue – in this issue – shows Muslims with turbans, camels and elephants. Han has adopted the original text except for a few minor changes.

B. Locations of the surviving originals of the two Marburg editions 1557

(according to Franz Obermeier, 2014, updated, see the note below)

Today, 27 existing originals of the two Marburg editions can be found in 9 countries, 10 of them in bundles.

Germany (11) + 3 lost

Staatsbibliothek Bamberg, BSB München, Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel, Märkisches Museum Berlin (lost), ULB Halle (lost), SLUB Dresden, SUB Göttingen, Commerzbibliothek der Handelskammer Hamburg, Staatsbibliothek Berlin (lost), Bosch-Brasiliensammlung Stuttgart, Staats- und Stadtbibliothek Augsburg (2x), Marienbibliothek Halle, Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt

Austria (3)

Universitätsbibliothek Graz, Österreichische Nationalbibliothek Wien (2x)

Schwitzerland (1)

Zentralbibliothek Zürich

Denmark (1)

Kongelige Bibliotek Kopenhagen

Sweden (1)

Kungliga Biblioteket Stockholm

England (1)

British Library London

Russia (1)

Russian National Library Sankt Petersburg

USA (5)

James Ford Bell Library Minnesota, Lilly Library at the Indiana University Bloomington, New York Public Library New York (2 x), Huntington Library San Marino (California)

Brazil (3)

Museo Paulista São Paulo, José Mindlin Collection at the Universidade de São Paulo, Biblioteca Nacional Rio de Janeiro

Update to Obermeier 2014: the Darmstadt copy has no specific provenance marks. The two newly discovered Augsburg copies are the two first editions: 4 Gs 2230 Mariä Geburt, 4 Gs 2231 Fasnacht. 4 Gs 2230 has a manuscript note proving the former ownership of the Augsburg Jesuit college, secularized after the suppression of the order in the 18th century and coming first to the Katholischer Bildungsfond Augsburg, later to the Staats- und Stadtbibliothek. A signature on the title page may refer to the estate inventory of Christoph Peutingen. 4 Gs 2231 has been state property from the secularization on, and as a doublet copy it was inventoried only in 1969.

Important provenances of early copies

Known as the first owner of the copy of the University Library in Tübingen (Frankfurt imprint) is Martin Crusius (1526-1607), a classical scholar and historian. He taught Greek and Latin as professor at the University of Tübingen. Numerous marginal notes by Crusius. Digital version: urn:nbn:de:bsz:21-dt-7969

First owner of the Halle copy, now in the Marienbibliothek (2nd Marburg edition), was Lampert Distelmeyer from Brandenburg, who had been working as a civil servant and diplomat at the court in Berlin since 1551, and acting as chancellor from 1558 to 1588. See Obermeier 2018.

The copy from the Bonn University and State Library (Frankfurt edition [1557]) came from the library of the well-known Brazilian traveler Maximilian von Wied-Neuwied (1782-1867).

In the 16th century a German Staden edition (probably an original one) was in the collection of the physician and collector Felix Platter (1536-1614), who had a rich natural history cabinet, a kind of cabinet of curiosities (Wunderkammer) in his hometown Basel. He lent it to the Brazilian traveller Jean de Léry (1534-1613) when the latter paid him a visit to Basel in 1586. Léry, who spoke no German, was able to read the most important parts with the help of a friend. In a later edition of his *Histoire*, (first edition, Geneva 1578), here the 4th edition, Geneva 1599/1600, he spoke very favourably of the book and emphasised the similarities with the observations in his own book (see the original passage and transl. in Staden, Studienausgabe, ed. F. Obermeier, German and Portuguese, academia.edu 2023, Appendix 5). The Platter collection was later dispersed and his copy is not extant or identified.

C. Reprints (according to Karl Fouquet, 1964 – revised, with additions and corrections.)

The work was soon reprinted. These version have been more or less carefully edited, some are mere retellings. Of course, the woodcuts of the original are usually missing (with the exception of the original woodcuts still partly used in Winckelmann, 1664) or have often been replaced by new illustrations using the originals as a template. Some parts of the work – dedication to the sovereign, foreword by Dryander, synopsis – are sometimes absent.

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|---------------------|---|
| [1557] Frankfurt | Warhaftige Historia, colophon: Gedruckt zu Franckfurdt am Mayn durch Weygandt Han in der Schnurgassen zum Krug. No year given (see above, with illustrations of Han's Varthema edition 1556). |
| 1561/1564 Hamburg | <i>Eine warhaftige Historia ...</i> Niederdeutsche Fassung. Version in Low German. The ed. 1561 is lost.
[Voucher copy: ed. 1564 Plantin-Moret-Museum, Antwerp], |
| 1567 Frankfurt/Main | In: <i>Ander theil dieses Weltbuchs von Schiff-fahrten ...</i> by Sebastian Franck von Wörd (ed. of the Weltbuch by Sebastian Frank, 1534, second volume), also separate print of this volume as <i>Neue Welt</i> . |
| 1592 Frankfurt | Memorabilis provinciae Brasiliae Historia, Bry, Latin edition followed by a German ed. next year. |
| 1593 Frankfurt/Main | <i>Drittes Buch Americae, Darinn Brasilia von</i> durch Johann Staden von Homburg auß Hessen ...
The 1592/93 editions form the 3rd part of the multi-volume travelogues collection by Theodor de Bry known as „America“ or Grand voyages (size: in folio). Two prints of the German version in 1593 (VD16 L 1294 and VD16 ZV 28334). |
| 1613 Frankfurt/Main | (2nd edition) [Publisher: Johann Theodor de Bry, son to Theodor de Bry] |
| 1624 Frankfurt/Main | (3rd edition) |
| 1631 Frankfurt/Main | In: <i>Historia Antipodum oder Neue Welt-Historie</i> by Johann Ludwig Gottfried [Publisher: Matthäus Merian] |
| 1640 Breslau | Staden's story is mentioned in a summary in a calender by David Fröhlich, Breslau 1640. Marginal note for January, Printer Georg Baumann. See: Sz. Kristof, Ildiko, Amerika und seine UreinwohnerInnen in den ungarischen Kalendern des 17. Jahrhunderts: David Frölich vs. die Jesuiten. In: Klaus Dieter Herbst - Werner Greiling (ed.): Schreibkalender und ihre Autoren in Mittel-, Ost- und Ostmitteleuropa (1540–1850). Bremen, Edition Lumiere, p.355-369. 2018, Ill. 12, mention p.367. |
| 1655 Frankfurt/Main | (2nd edition from the <i>Historia Antipodum</i> by Gottfried) |
| 1664 Oldenburg | In: <i>Der Americanischen Neuen Welt Beschreibung</i> by Hans Just Winckelmann, with some original woodcuts from the 1557 edition, and a new portrait of Staden (not authentic) |
| 1665 Frankfurt/Main | (3th Edition from the <i>Historia Antipodum</i> von Gottfried) |

- 1729 Frankfurt/Leipzig *Curieuses und besonderes Gespraech In dem Reiche derer Todten Zwischen Christophero Colombo ... und Johann Staden, eines gleichfalls geruehmten Deutschen See-und Schiff-Mannes* [Anonymous. Probably by David F. Fassmann, who in the tradition of the then popular *Dialogues of the Dead* according to the ancient model of Lucian invents a conversation between the two travelers, which is based, among other things, on the text of Staden, but with many errors. Only one copy survives (3rd edition) at the Martius-Staden Institute in São Paulo, it has been ed. as *Cristóvão Colombo e Johann Staden: um diálogo no reino dos mortos*; by Rosemarie E. Horch, Univ. de Sao Paulo, Inst. de Estudos Brasileiros 1992]
- 1859 Stuttgart In: *N. Federmann und H. Stades Reisen in Suedamerika ...*
Editor: Karl Kluepfel
- 1871 Hamburg *Hans Staden von Homberg bei den brasilianischen Wilden ...*
Editor: Robert Avé-Lallemant
- 1920 Buenos Aires In: *Zeitschrift des Deutschen Wissenschaftlichen Vereins/4.-6. Heft* - Publisher: Robert Lehmann-Nitsche
- 1929 Leipzig *Hans Staden, Ein deutscher Landsknecht in der neuen Welt ...*
Brockhaus. Alte Reisen und Abenteuer 23, new revision by Robert Lehmann-Nitsche
- 1934 Buenos Aires *Hans Stadens Wahrhaftige Historia und Beschreibung ...*,
(new revision by Gertrud Tudsén)
- 1941 São Paulo *Hans Staden. Zwei Reisen nach Brasilien ...*
Editor: Karl Fouquet
- 1963 Marburg (2nd, rev. Edition of 1941) *Hans Staden. Zwei Reisen nach Brasilien ...*) reprinted: 3. ed. 1970, 4th ed. 1981, 5th ed. 1995, from the 6th version 2011 on published by the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land, reprinted with a new introduction 2017 and 2022.
- 1964 Marburg *Hans Stadens Wahrhaftige Historia*
Editor: Reinhard Maack und Karl Fouquet
Original text and translation. Introduction, comments on the text, maps and bibliography
- 1982 Stuttgart *Brasilien – die wahrhaftige Historia der wilden ...*
[translated by Ulrich Schlemmer, published by Gustav Faber]
- 2004 Kelkheim/Taunus *In der Gewalt der nackten Menschenfresser ...*
[translated by Manfred-Guido Schmitz]
- 2017 Wolfhagen (7th updated edition of Fouquet 1941): *Hans Staden. Zwei Reisen nach Brasilien*. With a new preface by Wolfgang Schiffner and Franz Obermeier
- 2022 Wolfhagen 8th edition, reprint of the 7th edition 2017

D. Facsimile editions

- 1925 Frankfurt/Main *Hans Staden, Wahrhaftige Historia vnd Beschreibung ...*
Verlag Wüsten & Co. With an introduction (Begleitschrift),
by Richard N. Wegner
- 1927 Frankfurt/Main (2nd edition of the facsimile by Richard N. Wegner)
- 1978 Kassel *Hans Staden, Wahrhaftige Historia und Beschreibung ...*
Publisher: Thiele & Schwarz, Kassel. Edited with an
epilogue by Günther E.Th. Bezenberger
- 2007 Kiel As part of the critical edition of F. Obermeier

E. Digital editions (selection)

Only Text: <https://www.projekt-gutenberg.org/autoren/namen/staden.html>

First edition, first print, copy in the SUB Göttingen:

<http://gdz.sub.uni-goettingen.de/dms/load/toc/?PID=PPN235191442>

First print 1557: John Carter Brown library, archive.org; USP, São Paulo (Mindlin collection), SUB Göttingen, the John Carter Brown library has also the Weigand Han edition [1557], archive.org.

Second print 1557: Biblioteca nacional, Rio, archive.org.

Digital editions: Studienausgabe (study edition)

Portuguese:

2023 Hans Staden, *Historia de duas viagens ao Brasil (1548-1555)*. Tradução por Guiomar Carvalho Franco, revisada por Augusto Rodrigues. Com um anexo de fontes. Ed. de Franz Obermeier 2023 [Texto port. da ed. crítica de 2007, prefácio ampliado, com um novo anexo de fontes da época e comentários da iconografia], academia.edu 2023.

Parallel German edition for the German public:

2023 Hans Staden, *Warhaftige Historia. Zwei Reisen nach Brasilien (1548-1555)* Studienausgabe mit einem Quellenanhang. Hrsg. von Franz Obermeier. Übertragung ins heutige Deutsch: Joachim Tiemann 2023, academia.edu.

These two editions contain for the first time all available early sources to Staden with German or Portuguese translation and a commentary on the iconography of Staden and the Brys:

Anhang I. / Appendix I.

Zwei Briefe / Two letters

1.1. Hans Staden an Graf Wolrad II. von Waldeck, Wolfhagen, o. J. [1557]

Staatsarchiv Marburg 115.1 (Waldeck, Ältere Kanzleien, Gräfl. Personalien).

1.2. Hans Staden an [Graf Philipp Ludwig I. oder Graf Reinhard von Hanau-Münzenberg], o.O. o. J. [1557] Staatsarchiv Marburg 81 (Regierung Hanau) 31 A, Nr. 4. Nicht eig., behändigtes Schreiben; in fol.

1.3. Die einzige personengeschichtlich auf Staden beziehbare Quelle

Eine Pfändungsandrohung gegen einen Hans Staden aus Korbach 1558. Quelle: Staatsarchiv Marburg (StM), Schreiben des hessischen Statthalters Johann Keudel an den Richter zum Sachsenberg (Grafschaft Waldeck), Marburg 4 Juni 1558, Best 257, Fragmenta actorum, XXVII, Nr. 10, fol 68.

All version in original and translation in actual German.

2) Quellen von fremder Hand

Die Briefe von Juan de Salazar aus Santos und São Vicente. 1552/52, Sevilla, Archivo de Indias, in Spanish and German translation.

3) Schmidls Beschreibung seines Aufenthalts in São Vicente zu Stadens Zeit (Juli 1553) (Extract from / aus Ulrich Schmidel/Ulrico Schmidl, Wahrhaftige Beschreibung, entstanden 1554, erstmals veröffentlicht 1567, hier aus der Übersetzung des Autograph Schmidls ins Neuhochdeutsche, als Reise in die La Plata-Gegend, hrsg. und übertr. von Franz Obermeier, Straubing 2008, p.95/96).

4) Ein Brief von António Martins Penteado an den König. Eine bisher nicht bekannte Lissaboner Archivalie mit Bezug zu Stadens erster Reise nach Brasilien. 1548. Portuguese and German translation.

5) Das Urteil des zeitgenössischen Brasilienreisenden Jean de Léry, Verfasser der *Histoire d'un voyage fait en la terre du Brésil*, erstmals [Genf 1575] in einer späteren Auflage (4. Auflage 1599/1600) über seine Lektüre von Stadens Reisebuch um 1586. French and German.

Anhang II: Ethnographischer Annex und Kommentar zum Bildteil der Kannibalismusdarstellungen

Staden-Bry: ikonographischer Vergleich

Zeittafel zu Hans Staden und seiner Warhaftigen Historia

Indices zu Stadens Buch

F. Critical Edition

Hans Staden: Warhaftige Historia. Zwei Reisen nach Brasilien, (1648 – 1555) / Historia de duas viagens ao Brasil. Kritische Ausgabe / edição crítica: Franz Obermeier, translated by Joachim Tiemann. Tradução ao português: Guiomar Carvalho Franco. Revisão: Augusto Rodrigues, Kiel 2007.

With a facsimile of the original, a detailed introduction in German and Portuguese, comments and notes, with a detailed bibliography of research literature until 2007.

G. Translations

Dutch

For the Netherlands, Staden's work was interesting right from the very beginning.

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|------|-----------|--|
| 1558 | Antwerp | <i>Warachtige Historie ende Beschrijvinge ...</i> with new woodcuts
[Printer: Christoffel Plantijn] |
| 1563 | Antwerp | <i>VVarachtige Historie ende Beschrijvinghe ...</i> [Printer: Jan Roelants] |
| 1595 | Amsterdam | <i>Waerachtige Historie en beschrijuinge ...</i> [Printer: Cornelis Claesz] |

Religious reasons were also important and were sometimes mentioned in the book's title.

- | | | |
|------|-----------|---|
| 1625 | Amsterdam | <i>Hans Staden von Hombergs Beschrijvinghe van America ... Oock hoe Wonderbaerlick hy door de Hant des Heeren verlost is</i> [„Also how wonderfully he was redeemed by the hand of the Lord“.]
[Printer: Broer Iansz. He printed also the 2nd-7th edition of this book.] |
| 1627 | Amsterdam | (2nd edition) |
| 1630 | Amsterdam | (3th edition) |

From 1630 to 1654 the Dutch West Indian Company had a colony in Northern Brazil in the area around Pernambuco (today: Recife), where Staden had stayed during his first journey in 1548/49. The title alluded to Staden's importance for Dutch going to Brazil.

- | | | |
|------|-----------|--|
| 1634 | Amsterdam | (4th edition) with the hint: <i>.. is seet dienstigh voor de gene die naer Brasilien of Fernambucque varen ..</i> [This is very useful for the people who go to Pernambuco.] |
| 1638 | Amsterdam | (5th edition) |
| 1638 | Amsterdam | (6th edition) |
| 1640 | Amsterdam | (7th edition) |

Even after the end of the Dutch colony, the Dutch interest for Staden's History remains, as numerous reprints prove.

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|------|-----------|---|
| 1655 | Amsterdam | (8th edition) [Printer: Jan Jacobsz Bouman] |
| 1656 | Amsterdam | (9th edition) [Printer: Jan Jacobsz Bouman] |
| 1660 | Amsterdam | (10th edition) [Printer: Jan Jacobsz Bouman] |
| 1679 | Amsterdam | (11th edition) [Printer: Michiel de Groot] |
| 1685 | Utrecht | (12th edition) [Printer: Juriaen van Poolsum] |

- 1686 Amsterdam (13th edition) [Printer: Gijsbert de Groot]
 1701 Amsterdam (14th edition) [Printer: Gijsbert de Groot]
 1714 Amsterdam (15th edition) [Printer: Gijsbert de Groot]
 1736 Amsterdam (16th edition) [Printer: Witwe von Gijsbert de Groot]
- 1707 Leyden *De voorname Scheepstogten van Jan Staden Van Homburg ...*
 Pieter van der Aa published an extensive collection of sea voyages in Leyden in 1707 (29 volumes, in folio and in parallel in octave). Volume 15 contains Staden's work. In 1727 a second edition was published.

Latin

- 1592 Frankfurt/Main In: *America tertia pars memorabilem provinciae brasiliae Historiam continens ...* [Translated by Johann Adam Lonicerus]
 Published by Theodor de Bry, first edition, first print VD 16 ZV 14652
- 1592[?]
 Frankfurt/Main *America tertia pars*, first edition, second print [University library Rostock], other reprint 1605 [SLUB Dresden]

With these Latin Editions Staden's work was available for scholars as Latin was the common language used in Europe among them at that time.

French

- 1837 Paris *Véritable Histoire et Description d'un pays habité par les Hommes sauvages ...* [Translated by Henri Ternaux-Compans]
 The French researcher had studied in Göttingen and got to know the original there. Dryander's preface has been omitted.]

Portuguese

- 1892 Rio de Janeiro *Relação veridica e sucinta dos uzos e costumes dos tupinambás por Hans Staden* [From the French edition (1837)]
 translated by Tristão de Alencar Araripe
- 1900 São Paulo *Hans Staden. Sua viagem e captiveiro entre os selvagens ...*
 [Translated by Alberto Loefgren after the edition Marburg (1557). The first complete Portuguese edition]
- 1925 Rio de Janeiro *Hans Staden. Meu captiveiro entre os selvagens do Brasil*
 [„texto ordenado literariamente por Monteiro Lobato“, „Literary version“ of the first part by Monteiro Lobato. i.e. retelling close to the original]
- 1926 Rio / São Paulo (2nd edition)
 1927 São Paulo (3th edition)
- 1930 Rio de Janeiro *Viagem ao Brasil*. [Translation of the 2nd Marburg edition from 1557 by Alberto Loefgren]
- 1942 São Paulo *Hans Staden. Duas Viagens ao Brasil*. [Translated according to the first edition Marburg 1557 by Carlos Fouquet]
- 1945 São Paulo (4th edition of the year 1925)
 1955 Bahia (2nd edition of the year 1930)

Numerous new popular editions in Portuguese.

Spanish

- 1944 Buenos Aires *Vera Historia y Descripcion de un Pais de Salvages ... por Juan Staden* [Translated by Edmundo Wernicke]
 1945 Buenos Aires *Viajes y Cautiverio entre los Canibales por Hans Staden.* [Translated by Maria de Fernandes from the Portuguese edition (1900)]

Italian

- 1970 Milan *La mia Prigionia tra i Cannibali* [Translated by Amerigo Guadagnin]

English

- 1874 London *The Capivity of Hans Stade of Hesse* [!] [translated by A. Tootal]
 1928 London *The True History of his Captivity* [translated by Malcolm Letts]
 2008 Durham (USA) *Hans Staden's True History. An Account of Cannibal Captivity in Brasil.* Edited and translated by Neil L. Whitehead and Michael Harbsmeier.
 [Extensive introduction by the American anthropologist Neil L. Whitehead, annotated text in the translation by Michael Harbsmeier, all woodcuts, bibliography]

Other recent translations

- Czech by Vlasta Havlínová (1957, 2000)
 Japanese (by Toru Nishihara, transl. from the Portuguese, 1961)
 Danish by Ole Høiris (1992)
 Greek by Eleni Fameliadou-Nakou (1995)

B. The *Warhaftige Historia* as a book for young adults

The publication of the *Warhaftige Historia* by Klüpfel in 1859 led to retellings of the work in Germany. They were published as books for young readers and the "more mature youth", as it was then called.

- 1868 Leipzig In: *Wirkliche und wahrhaftige Robinsonaden ... Für die reifere Jugend, sowie für gebildete Familienkreise ...* p. 49-72:
Hans Staden aus Homberg unter den kannibalischen Tupinambas
 by Richard Andree
 1871 Hamburg *Hans Staden bei den brasilianischen Wilden oder die Macht des Glaubens und Betens*, published by Dr. Robert Avé-Lallemant
 [According to the title page, the book was also published in Reading, Pa. in the US]
 1911 Stuttgart *Deutsche Pfadfinder des 16. Jahrhunderts*, p. 35-77:
Hans Stadens Wahrhaftige Historia, published and processed by Max Pannwitz

- 1927 São Paulo *Aventuras de Hans Staden*
Retelling for Children by Monteiro Lobato in Portuguese
Reprinted in Brazil in over 30 editions.
Contributed decisively to the popularity of the work in Brazil.
- 1931 Berlin In: Abenteuer aus aller Welt - vol.3:
Neun Monate unter Menschenfressern, published by Heinrich Zimmermann and Hanns Gieseler
- 1967 Wuppertal *Ubatuba – Aus dem abenteuerlichen Leben des deutschen Brasilienfahrers Hans Staden*, by Kurt Salecker
- 1990 Wuppertal *In den Händen der Menschenfresser – die Abenteuer des deutschen Brasilienfahrers Hans Staden*, by Kurt Salecker [2nd slightly modified edition from 1967]

C. New retellings or fictional works inspired by Staden's story

- 2008 Frankfurt *Warum sie den Hans nicht fraßen – Das Geheimnis des Hans Staden*, by Hans Wilhelm Schäfer
- 2016 *Mit Gott bei den Menschenfressern – Und Luthers Geheimnis*
by Günther Augustin [Published as Book on demand or as E-Book]
- 2018 Lissabon *Hans Staden SUA ALMA – MINHA ALMA?*
De soldados lansquentes e outros aventureiros
by Detlef Günter Thiel. Novel inspired by Staden, translated to Brazilian Portuguese by Paula OZ. Published by EDIÇÕES OZ
- 2020 *Mit Gott bei Menschenfressern*
by Günther Augustin, 2nd extended edition from 2016
[Published as Book on demand or as E-Book]
- 2022 Wolfhagen *Hans Staden: Seine Seele - Meine Seele? Von Landsknechten und anderen Abenteurern*, by Detlef Günter Thiel, Wolfhagen: Litho 2022, original version of the Portuguese edition in 2018.

I. The Warhaftige Historia as a graphic novel

- 1979 Paris LIBRAIRIE LAROUSSE: LA DÉCOUVERTE DU MONDE EN BANDES DESSINÉES
(No. 8 of a 24-part series). In:
Au fil de l'Amazone les Européens au Brasil, p.374-384
Dessin de Jose Bielsa, scénario de Mino Milani.
- 1981 Bergisch Gladbach The French comic from 1979 was published in a German translation with the same cover photo by BASTEI COMIC: *Die Eroberung der Welt. Wie unser Erdball von mutigen Männern entdeckt wurde. ... Pinzon, Cabral, Hans Staden: Die Entdeckung Brasiliens.*
- 1992 Barcelona El cautivo, part of the series Europeos ante del Nuevo Mundo, colección del Quinto Centenario,
published by Planeta De Agostini 1992, sample page:
<http://365comicsxyear.blogspot.com/2014/09/0409-el-cautivo.html>.
Drawings by Ruben Pellejero, story by Jorge Zentner.

- 2002 Saint-Egrève *Le Captif* in French language (translation of the Spanish graphic novel by Ruben Pellejero and Jorge Zentner, translated by Pablo Guevara).
Saint-Egrève: Moskito.
- 2005 São Paulo *HANS STADEN. Un aventureiro no Novo Mundo* by Jô Oliveira
The complete story first appeared in this version in 3 issues of the Italian magazine *Corto Maltese*, 1989 (Ano 7, No. 7,8,9). Two book editions were published in Brazil, the 2005 edition by Conrad in black and white and the second, this time in colour, by Cortez Editora in 2013.
- 2010 Kassel *Hans Staden. Ich lebte unter Menschenfressern* by Albert Völkl

I. The Wahrhaftige Historia as movie

- 1971 Brasilien *Como era gostoso o meu francês* [„How tasty was my Frenchman“]
Director: Nelson Pereira dos Santos
- 1999 Brasilien *Hans Staden*
São Paulo Director: Luiz Alberto Pereira
Also offered as DVD-Video and available on YouTube. The film has won several film awards.

J. The Warhaftige Historia in Nordhessisch (North Hessian dialect)

- 1995 Kassel Schwarz uff wiß. Eine hessische Chronik in Kasseler Mundart von Lorenz Landsiedel. - Herausgegeben von Quirinus Quiddenbaum in Verbindung mit Werner Guth.
Separate chapter nr. 38 (p.81-86: *Unner Menschenfressern*)

II. Secondary literature

A. Dictionary entries

Berchem, Theodor: „Wahrhaftig Historia [...]“, in: Kindlers Literatur Lexikon, München 1974, 858-859, [reprint Deutscher Taschenbuch Verlag], vol.24, p.11060. 2nd edition 1988/92, 3th edition 2009.

Gareis, Iris, “Staden, Hans“, in: Literatur Lexikon. Autoren und Werke deutscher Sprache, edited by Walther Killy, 1988-1993, vol.11, p.128

Obermeier Franz, “Staden, Hans“ in: Neue Deutsche Bibliographie 24, p.784-785.
Digital access: <https://www.deutsche-biographie.de/pnd118798367.html#ndbcontent>

Gareis, Iris, “Staden, Hans“, in: Killy Literaturlexikon. Autoren und Werke des deutschsprachigen Kulturraums, edited by Wilhelm Kühlmann et al., 2nd edition 2011, Berlin & New York, vol. 11, p.156-157.

Schiffner, Wolfgang, “Staden, Hans“ in: Biographisch-Bibliographisches Kirchenlexikon, published by F.W. Bautz, Nordhausen 2014, vol. XXXV, Supplement XXII, columns 1345-1355.

B. Secondary literature

The older literature

Until 2007, scholarly literature on Staden and his *Warhaftige Historia* amounts to over 300 documents in the bibliography contained in the critical edition of Franz Obermeier (see above part I. F.). Here we will only refer to some important titles from 1989 onwards in chronological order.

- (1989) Wendt, Astrid: *Kannibalismus in Brasilien, Eine Analyse europäischer Reiseberichte und Amerika-Darstellungen für die Zeit zwischen 1500 und 1654* Frankfurt 1989. (Europäische Hochschulschriften Reihe XIX, Volkskunde Abt. B, vol.15.). Dissertation Univ. Tübingen.
- (1991) Neuber, Wolfgang: *Fremde Welt im europäischen Horizont, Zur Topik der deutschen Amerika-Reiseberichte der frühen Neuzeit* (Philologische Studien und Quellen, Heft 121), Berlin 1991.
- (1993) Jahn, Bernhard: *Raumkonzepte der frühen Neuzeit, zur Konstruktion der Wirklichkeit in Pilgerberichten, Amerikareisebeschreibungen und Prosaerzählungen*, Frankfurt 1993, (Dissertation, Univ. München)
- (1994) Harbsmeier, Michael: *Wilde Völkerkunde, andere Welten in deutschen Reiseberichten der Neuen Frühzeit*, (Historische Studien; 12), Frankfurt 1994.
- (1995) Frübis, Hildegard: *Die Wirklichkeit des Fremden, die Darstellung der Neuen Welt im 16. Jahrhundert*, Berlin 1995 (1992/3: Dissertation, Univ. Tübingen)
- (1995) Menninger, Annerose: *Die Macht der Augenzeugen, neue Welt und Kannibalen-Mythos* (Beiträge zur Kolonial- und Überseegeschichte; 64), Stuttgart 1995. (1993 Dissertation, Univ. Bamberg)
- (1997) Harbsmeier, Michael: Vom Nutzen und Nachteil des Studiums älterer Reiseberichte: Zur Wiederentdeckung Hans Stadens im 19. Und 20. Jahrhundert, in: *Die Wiederentdeckung Lateinamerikas, die Erfahrung des Subkontinents in Reiseberichten des 19. Jahrhunderts*, ed. by Walter L. Bernecker (Lateinamerika-Studien; 38), Frankfurt 1997, p.79-105.
- (1999) Schlechtweg-Jahn: *Magie, Religion und Wissenschaft, Hans Stadens Brasilien-Reisebericht von 1557*, in: *Artes im Mittelalter*, ed. by Ursula Schäfer, Berlin 1999, p.263-279.
- (2000) Neuber, Wolfgang: *Topik als Lektüremodell, Zur frühneuzeitlichen Texterschließung durch Marginalien – am Beispiel einiger Drucke von Hans Stadens Warhaftige Historia*, in: Thomas Schirren, Gerd Ueding (ed.), *Topik und Rhetorik. Ein Interdisziplinäres Symposium*, Tübingen 2000, p.177-197.
- (2000) Obermeier, Franz: *Brasilien in Illustrationen des 16. Jahrhunderts* (Americana Eystettensisa Ser. B, Monografias, estudios, ensayos; 11), Frankfurt 2000 https://macau.uni-kiel.de/receive/publ_mods_00000693.

- (2002) Kiening, Christian: Ordnung der Fremde. Brasilien und die theoretische Neugierde im 16. Jahrhundert, in: *Curiositas – Welterfahrung und ästhetische Neugierde in Mittelalter und früher Neuzeit*, ed. by Klaus Krüger, p.59-110.
- (2003) Hanenberg, Peter: *Legende einer Reise ins Brasilien des 16. Jahrhunderts*, in: *Portugal-Alemanha-Brasil, actas do VI. Encontro Luso-Alemão/ 6. Deutsch-Portugiesisches Arbeitsgespräch 2001*, ed. by António Henrique de Oliveira Marques, (Colecção Hespérides Literatura; 14), 2 vol., Braga 2003, vol.2, p.57-65.
- (2003) Kiening, Christian: *Alterität und Mimesis. Repräsentation des Fremden in Hans Stadens Historia*, in: *Nach der Sozialgeschichte; Konzepte einer Literaturwissenschaft zwischen historischer Anthropologie, Kulturgeschichte und Medientheorie*, ed. by Martin Huber and Gerhard Lauer, Tübingen 2000, p.483-507.
- (2003) Holdenried, Michaela: *Künstliche Horizonte, Alterität in literarischen Repräsentationen Südamerikas*, (Philologische Studien und Quellen; 183), Berlin 2003.
- (2004) Bôas, Luciana Villas: *Wild stories of a pious travel writer, the unruly example of Staden's Warhaftig Historia (Marburg 1557)*, in: *Daphnis*, 2004, p.187-212.
- (2000) Obermeier, Franz: Die Rezeption von Hans Stadens „Wahrhaftige Historia“ und ihre Ikonographie, in: *Jahrbuch Institut Martius-Staden*, São Paulo, 47/48.1999/2000, p.133-151. <https://macau.uni-kiel.de/content/index.xml>.
- (2004) Pinheiro, Teresa: *Aneignung und Erstarrung, Die Konstruktion Brasiliens und seiner Bewohnerin portugiesischen Augenzeugenberichten, 1500-1595*. Stuttgart 2004. Dissertation Paderborn.
- (2005) Büttner, Nils: *Bilder von „Grimmigen Menschenfressern Leuthen“ (Wolfenbütteler Arbeiten zur Barockforschung; 43)*, ed. by Johann Anselm Steiger, Wiesbaden 2005, vol.2, p.889-817.
- (2005) Obermeier, Franz: Zeitgenössische Dokumente zu Hans Stadens Aufenthalt in Südbrazilien und im brasilianischen São Vicente, in: *Jahrbuch Martius-Staden*, 2005, p.107-134. <https://macau.uni-kiel.de/content/index.xml?lang=de>.
- (2005) Obermeier, Franz: *Hans Staden und Ulrich Schmidel im brasilianischen Sao Vicente*. Dokumente zu Hans Stadens zweiter Brasilienreise und Ulrich Schmidels Rückreise nach Europa, in: *Jahresbericht des Historischen Vereins für Straubing und Umgebung* 107, p.73-128. <https://macau.uni-kiel.de/content/index.xml?lang=de>.
- (2005) Metcalf, Alida C.: *Go-betweens an the colonization of Brazil 1500-1600*, Austin 2005.
- (2005) Mahlke, Kirsten: *Offenbarung im Westen: frühe Berichte aus der neuen Welt*, Frankfurt 2005, Diss. Frankfurt/M.
- (2006) Kiening, Christian: *Das wilde Subjekt*, Kleine Poetik der Neuen Welt, (Historische Semantik , vol.9) Göttingen 2006, p.57-71, 123-131.

(2006) In June 2005, the first research conference on the *Warhaftige Historia* took place in Wolfhagen in the rooms of the Regional Museum. The lectures were published in the *Martius Staden Jahrbuch* (Yearbook), No. 53 (2006), p.9-59.

(Online via the homepage of the institute, access via the catalogue there.)

1. Münzel, Mark, Vier Lesarten eines Buches, zur Rezeption von Hans Stadens *Warhaftige Historia*.
2. Gerlach, Gernot, „Nun helfe Gott meiner seelen“ – Glaubenserfahrungen in der Reformationszeit.
3. Obermeier, Franz, Die Illustrationen in Stadens *Warhaftige Historia* von 1557.
4. Gawora, Dieter, Hans Staden sah schon, was wir heute erst für wichtig halten.

The new Literature

In connection with the publication of the critical edition of Franz Obermeier's *Warhaftige Historia*, an international conference took place in Wolfhagen in March 2007. The occasion was the first printing of the original edition 450 years ago. In parallel, an exhibition on the reception history was shown in the city's regional museum.

The exhibition (in collaboration with the Instituto Martius-Staden in São Paulo) was documented in a publication of the Regional Museum Wolfhager Land in German and Portuguese:

(2007) Schiffner, Wolfgang (together with Eckhard E. Kupfer, Franz Obermeier und Sven-Hinrich Siemers): *Unter Menschenfresser-Leuthen / Entre gentes antropófagas / Hans Stadens Brasilienbuch von 1557 / O livro de Hans Staden de 1557*, ed. by Sven-Hinrich Siemers, Wolfhagen 2007.

The lectures of the two-day event were published the following year:

(2008) Obermeier, Franz: *Die Warhaftige Historia – Das erste Brasilienbuch*. Akten des Wolfhager Kongresses zu 450 Jahre Hans-Staden-Rezeption. Kiel Westensee 2008.

Digital access: https://macau.uni-kiel.de/receive/publ_mods_00000400.

Content:

1. Franz Obermeier
Hans Stadens Brasilienbuch im 450. Jahr seines erstmaligen Erscheinens, der verkannte Klassiker? (Universitätsbibliothek Kiel)
2. Frank Lestringant
Les indiens tupinamba vus par Staden, Thevet et Lery (Université de Paris)
3. Alida C. Metcalf
Hans Staden: The consummate go-between (Trinity University San Antonio, Texas)
4. Marília dos Santos Lopes
Hans Staden im Kontext der portugiesischen Entdeckungsgeschichte (Universidade Católica portuguesa, Lissabon)

5. Teresa Pinheiro
Die Gefangenschaftsberichte von Hans Staden und José Anchieta zwischen Märtyrertum und suspense (Universität Chemnitz)

 6. Michael Harbsmeier
Johannes Dryander: Hans Stadens gelehrter Schatten? (Roskilde Universität, Dänemark)

 7. Neil L. Whitehead
Contemporary meanings and continuing relevance: Staden's text in Brazilian cultural imagination and anthropologies of the Americas
(University of Wisconsin, Madison, USA)

 8. Eckhard Kupfer
Das Martius-Staden-Institut und seine Bedeutung für Hans Staden im 20. Jahrhundert
(Director of the Martius-Staden-Institut in São Paulo)

 9. Joachim Tiemann
Staden 2007: Zur Übertragung des Originaltextes der neuen Ausgabe der „Warhaftige(n) Historia“ (OStDir. i. R., former teacher, later working at the Martius-Staden-Institut in São Paulo)

 10. Vanete Dutra Santana
Quem são os selvagen, afinal? desmitificando o bom-europeu
(scholarship holder, FU Berlin)

 11. Harald Thun
Hans Stadens Wiedergabe der „Wilden sprache“ (Prof. Romance department, Universität Kiel)

 12. Franz Obermeier: Stadens Festung heute [with pictures of the likely location of Staden's base on the island of Santo Amaro, where a whaling station was later built. These ruins are still in existence]
- (2008) Schiffner, Wolfgang: Das erste ausführliche Buch über Brasilien in Europa, Hans Stadens „Warhaftige Historia“ von 1557, in: *Jahrbuch des Landkreises Kassel*, 2008, p.47-53.
- (2009) Metcalf, Alida C.: Mapping the traveled space, in: e-JPH, Vol 7, Nr. 1
Digital access: <https://rice.academia.edu/alidametcalf>.
- (2010) Schiffner, Wolfgang: Die Indianer Brasiliens in der Erzählung und Beschreibung Hans Stadens. [...], in: *Jahresbericht des Historischen Vereins für Straubing und Umgebung*, 112/2010, p.189-212.
- (2011) Schäffauer, Markus Klaus: *Die Vision der Gegessenen: Hans Staden, Autor des Kannibalismus*. In: Alexandra Curvelo u. Madalena Simões (ed.): *Portugal und das Heilige Römische Reich (16.–18. Jahrhundert)*. Aschendorff, Münster 2011, p.105–126.
- (2011) Fechner, Fabian: Der Reisende als Lügner? Zur Wahrhaftigkeit in Hans Stadens „Warhaftiger Historia“ (1557), in: *Geschichtsblätter für Waldeck* 99, p.10-18.

- (2012) Fechner, Fabian: Zwischen „Fabel“ und „Historie“ – Beglaubigungsstrategien in Hans Stadens „Warhafter Historia“ (1557), in: *Innsbrucker Historische Studien* 28, p.129-141.
- (2012) Obermeier, Franz: Ein wiederentdeckter Hamburger Druck des 16. Jahrhunderts: die in Hamburg gedruckte niederdeutsche Hans-Staden-Ausgabe, in: *Auskunft* 2012, Heft 2, p.343-346. <https://macau.uni-kiel.de/content/index.xml>
- (2012) Duffy, Eve M. and Metcalf, Alida C.: *The Return of Hans Staden. A Go-between in the Atlantic World*, The John Hopkins University Press, Baltimore 2012.
- (2014) Obermeier, Franz: Deutsche Reiseliteratur über Südamerika im 16.Jahrhundert. Stadens Erstausgabe des Brasilienbuchs *Warhaftige Historia* (1557), das Reisegenre und seine Bildsprache in Sammlungskontexten, in: „Privater Buchbesitz in der Renaissance. Bild, Schrift und Layout“, in: *Kunsttexte* 3/2014, Heft 3, 2014. Digital access: <http://www.kunsttexte.de/2014>.
- (2015) In Wolfhagen, a two-day symposium on the importance of Stadens *Warhaftige Historia* took place. The lectures were published in 2016: The updated version was published in 2023 as an internet publication.

Schiffner, Wolfgang (Editor):

Ein Nordhesse entdeckt Amerika. Hans Stadens *Warhaftige Historia* von 1557.

Neues zum Werk des Brasilienreisenden, Fachtagung in Wolfhagen 2015,

Schriften des Vereins Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land Reihe Forschungen vol.11.

Ed. on behalf of the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land 2016, by Beate Bickel und Franz Obermeier. (228 pages). Corrected version 2023 / erweiterte und überarb. Auflage 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12568986>, published 2024.

Content:

1. Schiffner, Wolfgang: Hans Staden. Ein Leben in gefährlicher Zeit
2. Obermeier, Franz: Stadens Werk im Kontext der brasilianischen Geschichte
3. Obermeier, Franz: Hans Staden und sein Brasilienbuch. Ein Forschungsbericht zu neuerer Literatur und andere Stadenaktivitäten
4. Schiffner, Wolfgang: Ergänzungen zum Forschungsbericht von Franz Obermeier
5. Schäfer, Uwe: Die Bezeugung des Erlösers. Reformatorische Aspekte in Hans Stadens *Warhafter Historia*
6. Mendes, Alexandre E.: Zur Problematik der Darstellung von Kannibalismus in Text und Bild der *Warhaftigen Historia*
7. Barking, Sabrina: Die andere Kultur aus eurozentrischer Sicht. Alteritätserfahrungen in der *Warhaftigen Historia*

8. Fechner, Fabian: Zugelassene Ungewissheit. Die Darstellung von Grenzen des interkulturellen Verstehens in Kolumbus' Bordbuch und Hans Stadens *Warhafter Historia*

9. Schulz-Grobert, Jürgen. Goethe, Humboldt und die Brüder Grimm. Die Erfolgsgeschichte der Warhaftigen Historia im Spiegel ihrer (un-)bekannten Leserschaft

10. Schiffner, Wolfgang: Die *Warhaftige Historia* als Jugendbuch und Comic

11. Gawora, Dieter: Stadens *Warhaftige Historia* und die schwierige Wahrnehmung der Anderen

(2015) Schäfer, Uwe: Der errettete Beter. Hans Stadens „Warhaftige Historia“ (1557) als Protestantische Erbauungserzählung und Beispiel lebensbezogener Lutherrezeption Peter Lang, Frankfurt/Main 2015.

(2017) Richter, Sandra: Eine Weltgeschichte der deutschsprachigen Literatur, München 2017, p.52-57

(2018) Obermeier, Franz: Brasilien in Halle. Ein hessischer Brasilienreisender in der Sammlung der Marienbibliothek: Hans Stadens *Warhaftige Historia* von 1557. In: Erlebte Fremde. Reiseberichte aus der Frühen Neuzeit in der Marienbibliothek in Halle an der Saale, ed. by Jutta Eckle, Halle 2018, p.15-31

(2019) Andressa Inácio de Oliveira, Mulheres Brasilis, Mulheres platinas. As representações das mulheres tupi-guarani nas Histórias Verdadeiras de Hans Staden e Ulrich Schmidl, Master Tesis 2019. Researchgate.net.

(2019) In Staden's birthplace Homberg/Efze, a research conference was dedicated to the author and his work in 2017. The lectures were published:

Hans Staden – Sein Werk, seine Zeit und seine Wirkung. Beiträge der Homberger Stadentagung von 2017, ed. by Leandra A. Pohlai und Jürgen Schulz-Grobert, Cuvillier Verlag Göttingen 2019. (228 pages)

Content:

1. Schiffner, Wolfgang: Die Rezeption der *Wahrhaftigen Historia* in populären Bearbeitungen im 19. Jahrhundert bis heute - As an appendix a miscellanea: A letter from António Martins Penteado to the King (1548) with reference to Penteado, the captain of Staden's first trip to Brazil. Discovered by Detlev Günter Thiel in the National Archive, Lisbon.

2. Schröder, Kevin: *Der Kolumbus-Brief* als Quelle

3. Meckbach, Lisa Marie: Amerigos Brasilien-Bild – Mittelalterliche Überlieferungszeugnisse

4. Schulz-Grobert, Jürgen: *Vespucius ... vnd yetzt gedeütsch*. Edition, Übersetzung und ikonographische Kontextualisierung eines Neue Welt-Flugblatts

5. Metzsig, Gregor M.: Indiam zu besehen - Deutsche Söldner im portugiesischen Weltreich
 6. Fäcke, Christiane: André Thevet und Jean de Lery: Französische Reisebeschreibungen aus der „Neuen Welt“ zwischen Katholizismus und Calvinismus
 7. Schäfer, Uwe: Hans Stadens kirchliche Prägung – Vorläufige Überlegungen zur Vermittlung religiösen Wissens in der Reformationszeit am Beispiel eines hessischen Landsknechts
 8. Päsler, Ralf G.: Hans Staden auf See – Zur Praxis und Theorie der Seefahrt im 16. Jahrhundert
 9. Pohlai, Leandra A.: Naturkunde bei Hans Staden – Exemplarische Beobachtungen zu Fragen neuzeitlicher Tropenbiologie
 10. Krihl, Antonia: Reiseberichte im Mittelalter und der frühen Neuzeit – Ein Forschungsüberblick mit neuen Impulsen
- (2020) Ette, Ottmar: *ReiseSchreiben* – Potsdamer Vorlesungen zur Reiseliteratur, 2020 Boston/Berlin, p.297-308: Hans Staden oder das Leben an den Rändern einer sich globalisierenden Welt.
- (2022). Lina Herz / Bernd Bastert: Hans Staden unter brasilianischen *Tyrannen*. Europäisch-südamerikanische Verschlingungen in der Frühen Neuzeit. In: *Historisches Jahrbuch* 142 (2022), p.243-264.
- (2023) Franz Obermeier, Hans Stadens Brasilienbuch und die Prodigienliteratur - Stadenreflexe in populärer Literatur vom 16. bis zum 18.Jahrhundert. First held as conference Berlin 2008, published as updated version 2023, academia.edu.
- (2023) Franz Obermeier, John Whites Virginia 1585 und Hans Stadens Brasilien 1557. Die ersten Bilder aus der Neuen Welt *America*. Ein Essay, academia.edu
- (2023) Herz, Lina, Hans Staden in Hamburg: Die 'Warhaftig Historia' niederdeutsch. In: *Zeitschrift für deutsches Altertum und deutsche Literatur*, 152 (2023), (3), p.356-375.
- (2023) Kartenmaterial zum ersten Brasilienbuch, Hans Stadens Warhaftige Historia, Marburg 1557 / Mapas para Hans Staden, História de duas viagens ao Brasil, Marburgo 1557, academia.edu [the maps by Reinhard Maack are taken from the Staden ed. by Karl Fouquet, Marburg 1964].
- (2023) Die originale Karte in Hans Staden, Warhaftige Historia, Marburg 1557 über Brasilien / O mapa original em Hans Staden, Warhaftige Historia, Marburg 1557 sobre o Brasil, commentary: Franz Obermeier, academia.edu.
- (2024) Obermeier, Franz, *Gesammelte Schriften*, Bd. 1: Hans Staden, Warhaftige Historia, 2024, academia.edu. [Compilation of essays by the author on the topic]

Works by students

1. Published

- (2009) Schulz, Katja: Gottlose Menschenfresser oder gute Wilde – Das Indiobild in den Amerikaberichten des 15. Und 16. Jahrhunderts (Seminararbeit WS 2008/09) GRIN Verlag 2009
- (2009) Nauer, Heinz: Ein gemachter Bestseller? – Hans Stadens „Wahrhaftig historia“ von 1557 im Kontext der deutschen Südamerikaliteratur der Zeit (Masterseminararbeit Universität Luzern 2009), GRIN Verlag 2009
- (2011) Ehrngruber, Martina: Zwischen Kannibalismus und Kommerz – Der Vorwurf des Kannibalismus in Hans Stadens Reisebericht „Warhaftige Historia“ (Schriftliche Hausarbeit an der Fernuniversität Hagen 2011), GRIN Verlag 2011

2. Not published:

(available in the library of the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land, Wolfhagen)

- (1990) Toscano del Banner, Andreas, Frühe Darstellungen Amerikas, Hans Stadens "Wahrhaftige Historia", Magisterarbeit, Kunstgeschichte München LMU 1990. Published in an abridged version in: Staden Jahrbuch, São Paulo 1989/90, published 1992, p.50-73.
- (2008) Mittermayr, Sarah: Die Verarbeitung des Eigenen und des Fremden in Hans Stadens ‚Warhaftig Historia‘ (Diplomarbeit zur Erlangung des Magistergrades an der Universität Salzburg – Fachbereich Germanistik – Gutachter Prof. Dr. Ulrich Müller).
- (2009) Korf, Sabrina: Alteritätserfahrung im Spiegel der Wahrhaftigen Historia des Hans Staden (1557).
(Wissenschaftliche Hausarbeit im Rahmen der ersten Staatsprüfung für das Lehramt an Gymnasien im Fach Geschichte – Prüfstelle Kassel – Gutachterin: Prof. Dr. Renate Dürr).
- (2013) Mendes, Alexandre Emanuel: Die Neue Welt in Text und Bild – Die Beziehung zwischen Text und Illustration am Beispiel des Reiseberichts *Warhaftig Historia* von Hans Staden (Hausarbeit im Rahmen eines Masterseminars an der Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf).
- (2014) Bamert, Manuel: Von Tuppin Jmbas, Piranhäs und Canelas – Semantik und narrative Strukturen in Stadens *Warhaftiger Historia* im Vergleich mit zeitgenössischen Erlebnisberichten (Master-Seminararbeit an der Universität Zürich- Deutsches Seminar, Prof. Dr. Hildegard Elisabeth Keller).
- (2014) Mendes, Alexandre Emanuel: Intermediale Darstellungen von Kannibalismus in Hans Stadens Reisebericht *Warhaftige Historia* (1557)
(Masterarbeit im Fach Germanistik zur Erlangung des Grades Master of Arts (M.A.) der philosophischen Fakultät der Heinrich-Heine-Universität Düsseldorf – Prüfer: Holger Ehlert M.A.).

III. Reception history of Staden's Warhaftige Historia

A. Exhibitions

The exhibition in Wolfhagen in 2007 was planned as a travelling exhibition. In the following years it was shown in 8 places. Information can be obtained on the website: regionalmuseum-wolfhager-land.de with keyword input.

(2008) - Homberg/Efze

- July: Museum in Korbach

- August: Köln on the occasion of the Deutsch-Brasilianische Wirtschaftstage

- September: Husum Nordfrieslandmuseum Nissenhaus with more objects on display

(2009) Lahr and Stuttgart.

(2010) Tübingen, together with an exhibition by the Brazilian artist Raul Cassou

<https://www.raulcassou.com.br/>

(2011) The last place for the exhibition was in the Museum im Hospital in Grünberg. Here the museum has its own department with the collection of the German ethnologist Theodor Koch-Grünberg, who from 1898-1905 took part in several research trips to Brazil.

In Brazil the exhibition was shown from 2007 to 2008 in

- São Paulo, Colégio Visconde de Porto Seguro, Schuleinheit I

- Valinhos (Campinas), Schuleinheit II

- Florianópolis, City library

- Curitiba, Club Concorde

- Itanhaém, Museum

- Bertioga, Forte de São João

- Recife, Museum

- Fortaleza, Casa de Cultura Alemã

- Porto Alegre, Goethe-Institute

- São Paulo, University Library Florestan Fernandes

(2010) Juli: A new exhibition was presented in the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land:

„Tentoonstelling / Ausstellung / "Jan Staden en de Nederlanden / Hans Staden und die Niederlande“ On display was an original of the Dutch translation from 1706 with new copper engravings. To this end, a few examples were used to illustrate how since de Bry the iconography of the illustration of the Staden text in the Netherlands developed. [Here you see one example of those engravings.]

- (2011) In Wolfhagen, another exhibition was shown in the following year at the Regionalmuseum Wolfhager Land in October: "Hans Staden in Comic und Jugendbuch". Many originals were presented to demonstrate the reception of the *Warhaftige Historia* in adaptations from 1868 to 2010.
- (2018) The *Warhaftige Historia* was part of one exhibition in Halle, Marienbibliothek: see the publication „Erlebte Fremde – Reiseberichte aus der Frühen Neuzeit in der Marienbibliothek zu Halle an der Saale“, p. 99, ed. by Jutta Eckle, Halle 2018 [with the contribution p.15-31: Franz Obermeier: Brasilien in Halle... (2018)].
- (2022) Exhibition in Wolfhagen. „Wen interessiert denn sowas? Hans Stadens Brasilienreisen im 16. Jahrhundert“. The Halle copy was presented to a wider public in this exhibition, accompanied by a series of lectures. See for instance Franz Obermeier, conference, Wolfhagen 27.09.2022: Das neu entdeckte Exemplar einer Erstaussgabe von Hans Stadens Erlebnissen in Brasilien im 16. Jahrhundert und weitere Zeugnisse zu frühen Lesern:
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CG_-GvWghBI.

B. Staden's *Warhaftige Historia* as part of exhibitions

- (2007) At the DOKUMENTA 12 in Kassel (16.06-23.09) the video installation „Funk Staden“ by Mauricio Dias and Walter Riedweg was presented at the Schloss Wilhelmshöhe. See below.
- (2008) *Blutige Geschichten. Ein kulturhistorischer Streifzug durch die Welt der Verbrechen. Bloody stories. [A cultural-historical survey into the world of crime]* Exhibition in the State Hall of the Austrian National Library in Vienna 08.05 - 02.11.2008. Among other books the exhibition showed a copy of the *Warhaftige Historia* from the library's holdings. The pubic zone of women on the woodcuts were blackened by an unknown person. The book comes from a Library of Jesuits.

[The catalogue under the above title was published by the publisher MHM, Zell am Moos, 2008. About Staden see p.40/41 and on p.198-205 the article by Judit Zeller: *Ich hab dich zum Fressen gern. Anmerkungen zum Tabuthema Kannibalismus*]

(2012) Hessen Hybrid. Vom Kommen und Gehen in 5 Jahrhunderten. Exhibition 01.04-25.11. 2012. Freilichtmuseum „Der Hessenpark“ Neu-Anspach/Taunus. Later 2014 also in the Museum für Kunst und Kulturgeschichte der Philipps-Universität Marburg im Landgrafenschloss. The *Warhaftige Historia* is referred to as the first example of a Hessian who, through his work, represents the European view on the cannibals in South America.

[The catalogue under the above mentioned title has been published by the Freilichtmuseum Hessenpark, 2012]

(2017) Dahin, wo der Pfeffer wächst. Reisende vor 500 Jahren. Exhibition: Kultur- und Stadthistorisches Museum Duisburg vom 25. Juni bis 05. November 2017. Ulrich Schmidl and Hans Staden were mentioned as travel writers about South America. [Internet: <https://www.stadtmuseum-duisburg.de/dahin-wo-der-pfeffer-waechst-reisende-vor-500-jahren>]

C. The *Warhaftige Historia* in the media

Texts and radio shows on Hans Staden and his *Warhaftige Historia* appear repeatedly in the media. We mention only a few of them. The quality of the content varies greatly.

(2009) 31.10.2009: The German broadcasting station WDR transmitted a cultural feature: „Von Seelen- und Menschenfressern“ - Author: Andreas Weiser. The programme emphasizes links between Tupinamba cannibalism and European cannibalism.

(2011) Weiser, Andreas: Kannibalen? Wir? Gott bewahre! (GEO 04 / April 2011, p.81-88, with 9 woodcuts from the original).

(2013) Neumann, Jan Hendrick: „Ich euer Essen, komme“, Hans Staden – Vom fast verspeisten Söldner zum Ethnologen und Naturforscher (culture – art – fashion- people – story – photo EDITION Nr 1, Kassel, Silber Druck, p.60-63)

(2013/2023) “Staden”, *Zeitzeichen* August 2, 1553 - Staden gerät unter Kannibalen, “Stichtag”, Author: Heiner Wember, www.heinerwember.de, Producer: WDR 2013, <https://www1.wdr.de/stichtag/stichtag7690.html>. Retransmitted by Deutschlandfunk as “Kalenderblatt”, <https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/kalenderblatt-100.html>, August 2, 2023.

(2015) Karl-Ludolf Hübener: Als hessischer Landsknecht in Brasilien. Das abenteuerliche Leben des Hans Staden, German Broadcasting station SWR2, series: Wissen. Broadcasted Mai 22, 2015 at 8.30 am

(2016) Bruhns, Annette: Ein Reich aus Zucker und Gold – Brasilien als Filiale Portugals (Der Spiegel – Geschichte, Februar 2016 – p.20-30 with 4 colored woodcuts from the original).

D. Monuments dedicated to Staden

About these monuments see an article on the internet:

Franz Obermeier/Wolfgang Schiffner: Hans Staden und die Erinnerungskultur an die frühe Entdeckungszeit. Stadendenkmäler in Deutschland und Brasilien, online-publication 2019.

Digital access:

https://www.academia.edu/40684685/Hans_Staden_und_die_Erinnerungskultur_an_die_fr%C3%BChe_Entdeckungszeit

The locations of those monuments are the following cities:

Brazil

- *Itanhaém* Bas-relief (1988), Artist: Heinz Budweg: Staden's arrival in Itanhaém fenced in, but freely visible
- *Bertioga* Statue of Staden alongside with one Carijo-Indianer (2008), Artist : Gilmar Munhoz
Parque dos Tupiniquins by the fortress of Bertioga, accessible during the opening times
- *Boiçucanga* drawings after the *Warhaftigen Historia*, freely visible
- *Ubatuba* memorial stone with badge, freely visible

Germany

- *Homberg* Stadendenkmal as bas-relief (1957), at the town hall, freely accessible
- *Wolfhagen* Stadendenkmal as bas-relief (1976), at the *Hans-Staden-Straße*
Artist: Wilhelm Haarberg
(damaged 2020, not to be replaced or restored.)
- *Wolfhagen* Hans Staden as a bronze sculpture (2018), on the *Hospitalplatz*
Artist: Karin Bohrman-Roth, together with reliefs on a *Stadenpfad*.

E Staden inspiring art works

The artists of Staden's influential illustrations in the editio princeps are not known. The woodcuts were made following instructions of Staden or at least in close contact with him, as they give supplementary visual information to the text. Furthermore, Staden notes in the Errata in the first edition, that the mirrored copying of 5 woodcuts (alluding to the coastlines in one woodcut) is erroneous. Maybe this is a sign that the illustrations haven't been made in Marburg, but by some artists living elsewhere and not directly supervised by Staden. Compared to the French book illustrations in contemporary travel books to Brazil (see Obermeier 2000) they seem primitive to us, but they had a huge influence through the Bry versions in the America collection, combined there with iconographic elements from Jean de Léry (*Histoire d'un voyage fait en la terre du Brésil*, Geneva, 1578, 2.ed. 1580).

The Bry copperplates in the manierist style were copied by artists such as Matthäus Merian (Gottfried see above 1631), who was the son-in-law of Johann Theodor de Bry and thus inspired travel collections up to the 18th century. The Bry illustrations reappear nowadays in every historical book about the age of discovery and are available in various collections of the Bry illustrations for instance: *America de Bry: 1590 - 1634*; *Amerika oder die Neue Welt; die "Entdeckung" eines Kontinents in 346 Kupferstichen*, ed. by G. Sievernich: Berlin: Casablanca 1990 and recently in *Theodor de Bry - America: sämtliche Tafeln 1590-1602*, ed. by Michiel van Groesen and Larry E. Tise, Cologne: Taschen 2019.

The last use of the original woodcuts (incomplete because probably partly lost at that time) is to be found in Winkelmann 1664, (see above). Winkelmann also adds an apocryphal Staden portrait by an unknown artist, inspired by his figure on the original woodcuts.

The concept of Anthropophagy became a main metaphor in Brazilian art creatively appropriating Europe-centered artistic concepts and devouring them in order to produce something specifically Brazilian in the *Semana de Arte moderna de São Paulo* in 1922. However it is not clear if the participating artists knew Staden directly. Oswald de Andrade cites Montaigne's *Des cannibales*, from his *Essais* 1580 in his influential Manifesto antropófago in 1928 (first published in his *Revista de antropofagia* 1928) but does not mention Staden.

Among 20th century artists dealing with the Staden illustrations we have to mention Cândido Portinari (1903-1962) who prepared woodcuts for an English Staden edition in the 1940th, which was never released. These works were first published as: *Portinari devora Hans Staden*, São Paulo: Ed. Terceiro Nome in 1998.

The Brazilian artist José de Quadros, born in Barretos in 1958, having studied in Kassel, living and working in Kassel and São Paulo, was inspired by Staden in a series of works shown in Homberg and later in 2007 in Wolfhagen. The exhibition catalogue: *Maria Rosa trifft Hans Staden*, in der Stadtkirche zu Homberg/Efze und im Rathaus der Stadt Homberg/Efze. He combines approaches of Staden woodcuts with fotos by one of the last surviving members of the Brazilian Xavantes tribe, an old woman known as Maria Rosa. (see http://josedequadros.com/texte_de/mariarosa_1.html).

At the DOKUMENTA 12 in Kassel (16.06-23.09) the video installation „Funk Staden“ by Mauricio Dias and Walter Riedweg was presented at the Schloss Wilhelmshöhe. It showed funk dancers in Rio de Janeiro performing wild dances. The woodcuts on cannibalism taken from the *Warhaftige Historia* are here intended to illustrate the connection between ritual cannibalism and extreme violence, glorifying music from the drug scene. (Digital access: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vfzI2YeltWGI>) see [Conversation with the artists in: *Kunstforum International*, Volume 187, p.458-463, unfortunately with many false statements about Staden and his work].

Modern Brazilian graphic artist Gustavo Piqueira (www.gustavopiqueira.com.br) produced a set of books also partly inspired by Staden. Passages of Staden's travel book to Brazil are combined with 7 other partly fictitious travel accounts and present in an edition itself an artwork consisting of 8 fascicles in a slipcase (*Oito viagens ao Brasil*, WMF Martins Fontes / Biblioteca Brasileira Guita e José Mindlin 2017, book edition in one volume 2021. <https://www.gustavopiqueira.com.br/oito-viagens-ao-brasil>). In this work fictitious travelers become interrelated through the various volumes. The original Staden text in translation is combined with actual fotos of Ubatuba, a town in Brazil near Rio named after an indigenous village mentioned by Staden.

Indigenous postcolonial Brazilian artist from Amazonia, Denilson Baniwa (born in a village at the Rio Negro, Amazonas in 1984), uses elements of Staden's work in the Bry version. He wrote a manifesto in 2019 intitled „ReAntropofagia“ about the postcolonial appropriation of art: <https://brooklynrail.org/2021/02/criticspage/ReAntropofagia> (available in Engl. and Port.) He became known when he walked as the persona Pajé-Onça through the São Paulo Biennial in 2018, to which he was not officially invited, with a maraca and a traditional dress, stressing the absence of indigenous artists and the persistence of European visions of Indians. During the performance he tore apart the exhibition catalogue to protest against this lacuna: (Hackeando a 33 Bienal de Artes de SP, filmed version at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MGFU7aG8kgI>). For his artworks he uses new social media (<https://www.behance.net/gallery/76653681/Estampas-Indigenas>) and participates in international Art events such as the 22. Biennial of Sidney in 2020. <https://www.biennaleofsydney.art/participants/denilson-baniwa/>

Another internationally recognized artist using Bry-elements in sculpture and installations is renowned Brazilian artist Adriana Varejão, born in Rio in 1964. (<http://www.adrianavarejao.net/>). In Germany her work was recently shown in a group exhibition at the Munich Haus der Kunst. (catalogue: *Interiorities*: Njideka Akunyili Crosby, Leonor Antunes, Henrike Naumann, Adriana Varejão, ed. by Njideka Akunyili Crosby, Munich: Prestel, [2020].

Freelance Director Nora Mansmann is preparing a play about German-Brazilian relations on behalf of the Staatstheater Kassel. Representation is projected for 2025. Staden is to be included.

Note:

The authors of this bibliography are grateful for indications about newly discovered original editions of Stadens or other important contributions to the topic.

Wolfhagen/Kiel 2025